

AWARENESS AND ACCEPTABILITY OF THE REVISED PNU VISAYAS VISION, MISSION, GOALS, AND OBJECTIVES

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the level of awareness and acceptability of the revised vision, mission, goals, and objectives of the programs of Philippine Normal University Visayas as evaluated by students, faculty, administrative staff, alumni, and stakeholders. The result of the study provides an insight into the awareness and acceptability of the university's VMGO. Descriptive research was used and online survey method was followed. Data were collected using a researcher-made questionnaire designed from the university's vision, mission, goals, and objectives. The data were analyzed using percentage and rank to determine their awareness and acceptability of the VMGO. For the awareness of respondents, the data showed that the respondents with ranks 1 and 66.6 % were fully aware of the VMGO. The respondents possessed a very high level of acceptability with 58.7 % as rank 1. It is recommended that the university shall continue the awareness campaign and promote the VMGO for other stakeholders to be aware and enhance the acceptability level. Web administrators should maximize the use of the university website to get the widest dissemination of VMGO. The official University Facebook should increase and continue to disseminate information about VMGO. Evaluation on awareness and acceptability of the VMGO by the various stakeholders should be implemented periodically.

Keywords: *Acceptability, Goals, Mission, Objectives, Vision*

INTRODUCTION

The PNU Visayas VMGO serves as the cornerstone of an educational institution. The vision, mission, goals, and objectives serve as the cornerstone of an educational institution. A vision is a statement about what the organization wants to become and therefore resounds with all the members of the institution and helps them have a sense of ownership and become part of the entire organization. It provides the impression, character, and direction of its operations. Universities and Colleges created by and operated under the law are found by the permission of their charter and may not be as ready and flexible as private entities. For a university seeking accreditation, the area VMGO is the most fundamental of all the Areas surveyed (Castillo, RC. 2014). Any university undergoing an accreditation is likely to be more successful in achieving in-depth learning when leaders work with staff and the community to build a collective educational vision that is clear for all. It is assumed that a good vision and mission statement drives strategy and repositions organization, motivates and infuses greater performance among employees (Alquizalas, AG. 2019. The Accrediting Agency for Chartered Colleges and Universities in the Philippines (AACCUP) possessed a certain standard of quality excellence based on the institutional operations of VMGO. A university is judged by the degree to which its VMGO is attained and not in comparison with others on the needs of the program constituencies. Accrediting Agency for Chartered Colleges and Universities in the Philippines (AACCUP) possessed a certain standard of quality excellence based on the institutional operations concerning VMGO. The purpose of this study is to review the mission, vision, goals, and objectives of the campus every year or a few years to assess whether it is making progress toward its goals and reconfirm its commitment and mandate. In this process, the university may choose to revise the statements to better reflect its values which is truth, excellence, and service.

Research Questions

To give light to the problem, the researchers sought to answer the level of awareness and acceptability of the revised Philippine Normal University Visayas VMGO

1. How may the profile of the respondents be described?
2. What is the awareness level of the Revised PNU Visayas Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives when taken as a whole.
3. What is the acceptability level of the Revised PNU Visayas Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives when taken as a whole.
4. What are the challenges experienced by the respondent in the awareness drive/promotion of PNUV VMGO?
5. Based on the findings of the study, what recommendations may be proposed for the awareness and acceptability of the PNU Visayas VMGO?

Significance of the Study

The results of the study could provide valuable information and insights to the Philippine Normal University Visayas administrators, faculty, staff, students, benefactors, and future researchers to use as guidelines to conduct awareness seminars, and related activities relevant to Vision, Mission, Goal, and Objectives of an institution.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Descriptive survey research was employed in this study to determine the level of awareness and acceptability among students, faculty, staff, and other stakeholders on the vision, mission, goals, and specific objectives of the curricular programs. A researcher-made questionnaire was designed based on the existing VMGO of the institution and validated and conducted for validity and reliability with results of 4.98 indicating a high degree of validity and 0.981 Cronbach Alpha value. The emerging data collection approach based on internet/e-based technology Google Form was used (Regmi PR.2016). This is a relatively cost-effective survey alternative. These novel data collection processes can collect an enormous amount of data from participants in a short time frame. Data were summarized using weighted mean as the primary tool for the analysis of data.

Research Locale and Participants

A total of 530 respondents participated in the study composed of students, teachers, administrative staff, alumni, and other stakeholders of Philippine Normal University Visayas, in Cadiz City, Negros Occidental.

Research Instrument

The researcher-made questionnaire underwent validation with five experts, the head of the PNUV Quality Assurance Office, the former Executive Director & Provost, the Associate Dean of the Faculty of Graduate Studies, Teacher Education and Research, the Dean and the Associate Dean of Faculty Teacher Development Office. The Awareness and Acceptability Questionnaire of the Revised PNUV VMGO was used. It was divided into three parts. Part 1 was the respondents' profile, part 2 was the awareness level, and part 3 was the level of acceptability. After getting the validity, a reliability test was conducted to 25 persons who were not part of the actual respondents.

Data Gathering Procedure

The instrument assessed for validity and reliability used Cronbach Alpha. After an excellent result was obtained, the necessary permission from the research committee for accreditation to conduct the study to the respondents was secured. Data collection and processing procedures were carefully planned to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the data. Subsequently, quantitative data analyses were conducted.

Data Analysis

The study follows the ethical standard of research. After gathering all the data, the researchers used the Percentage, Rank and Pie chart.

RESULTS

This part includes the results on the Awareness and Acceptability of the VMGO of Philippine Normal University Visayas.

Table 1 *Percentage and Rank of the respondents according to gender*

Gender	%	Rank
Female	76.4	1
Male	21.3	2
Prefer not to say	1.7	3
Others	0.6	4
Total	100	

Figure 1 *Percentage Distribution of Respondents according to gender*

Table 2 Percentage and Rank of the respondents according to category

Category	%	Rank
Student	91.7	1
Teacher	3.4	2
Administrative Staff	1.3	4
Alumni	3.0	3
Other Stakeholders	0.6	5
Total	100	

Figure 2 Percentage distribution of respondents according to category

Table 3 Awareness level of respondents to the revised PNU Visayas VMGO

Category	%	Rank
Not aware at all	1.7	4
Slightly aware	9.2	3
Moderately aware	22.5	2
Fully aware	66.6	1
Total	100	

Figure 3 Percentage level on the Awareness of respondents to the revised PNU Visayas VMGO

Table 4 Acceptability Level of respondents on the revised PNU Visayas VMGO

Category	%	Rank
Very Low	0	4.5
Low	0	4.5
Average	7.5	3
High	33.8	2
Very High	58.7	1
Total	100	

Figure 4 Percentage Level on the Acceptability of respondents to the revised PNU Visayas VMGO

DISCUSSION

Table 1 showed the distribution of respondents according to gender. It showed that female respondents have a percentage of 76.4 or ranked 1, while the male has a percentage of 21.3 or ranked 2. Respondents who preferred not to say their gender have a percentage of 1.7 or ranked 3 and others have 0.6 percent or ranked 4. Therefore, the majority of the respondents were female. Figure 1 also shows the percentage results using the pie chart.

Table 2 showed the distribution of respondents according to category. It showed that students have a percentage of 91.3 or ranked 1. The teacher respondents have a percentage of 3.4 or ranked 2. Alumni respondents have a percentage of 3.0 or ranked 3, administrative Staff has a percentage of 1.3 or ranked 4, and other stakeholders have 0.6 percent or ranked 5. Therefore, the majority of the respondents were students. Figure 2 also shows the percentage results using the pie chart.

Table 3 presented the awareness level of the respondents. The respondents' awareness level on revised VMGO showed "fully aware" with a percentage of 66.6 or ranked 1, moderately aware with 22.5 percent or ranked 2, slightly aware 9.2 or ranked 3, and not aware at all 1.7 percent or ranked 4. Therefore, the majority of the respondents were fully aware of the revised VMGO. Figure 3 using a pie chart shows the percentage. This conformed with the findings of Lacaba (2016), results of the study revealed that students were generally "much aware" of the VMGO of the university. Filesilda (2019) stressed that the students were very highly aware of which produced world-class graduates. Bentor (2017) stressed that the students in Naval state University are aware of its vision, mission, goals and objectives and that these students understand and accept these statements, along with the responsibility of realizing such objectives in their own capacities. Estrada (2018) revealed that the level of awareness of internal stakeholders on the VMGO of PSU, administrators, faculty and staff, non-teaching staff and students are very highly aware. All three groups of respondents have the highest weighted Mean on the statement's awareness on vision and lowest mean on institutional goals.

Table 4 presented the acceptability level of the respondents. The respondents' acceptability level on the revised VMGO was very high with a percentage of 58.7 or ranked 1, high with 33.8 percent or ranked 2, average of 7.5 or ranked 3, and low and very low have zero percent ranked or 4.5. The figure 4 also shows the percentage of the respondents acceptability level. Therefore, the majority of the respondents possessed a very high acceptability level on the PNU Visayas VMGO. This conformed with the findings of Filesilda (2019) that the student's level of acceptability on the USEP's VMGO was highly acceptable, and the results were applied in their daily activities. Estrada (2018) findings revealed that the internal stakeholders generally understand and accept the vision, mission and institutional objectives of PSU as very highly acceptable. Furthermore, external stakeholders generally accept that the vision, mission and institutional objectives of PSU are clearly stated and the expected outcomes in terms of research and extension capabilities of students and graduates is highly acceptable.

The respondents possessed full awareness on the revised VMGO. A very high acceptability level of the vision and mission of the institution was revealed, as well as the goals of the college. Furthermore, students were “fully aware” of its program objectives. It can be implied from the results that students were properly informed of the VMGO of the university which can be attributed to the practice of integrating the VMGO in the syllabi of the faculty and is introduced as the first lesson in every subject. Moreover, the posting of VMGO in conspicuous or strategic places particularly in the classroom made it accessible for students to read the content of the VMGO. In addition, the printing of VMGO in students’ magazines, bulletin of information, students’ manuals, annual reports, and other school programs created awareness on the existence of VMGO. Lastly, VMGO was presented and discussed during the orientation program of the university

The Challenges in the awareness and acceptability drive/promotion of the revised PNU Visayas VMGO

On the challenges encountered in the awareness and acceptability drive/promotion of PNU Visayas VMGO, the following were drawn from the respondent’s answers. Some students do not reflect the university’s VMGO in their daily activities due to limited understanding and clarity of their meaning especially to new students. There are limited resources and financial allocations in the promotion of VMGO in the community. Future-ready pre-service teacher needs to understand the VMGO for they serve as leaders in the community. Being an EGTE (Environment and Green Technology Hub) of the Philippine Normal University Hub, conservation, and preservation of energy shall be emphasized as to why electricity is inaccessible during a specific time of the week. It becomes a challenge in the teaching and learning process where everyone is dependent on technology and internet connectivity.

Conclusions

Based on the study’s findings, the researcher came up with the following conclusions. On the level of awareness and acceptability of the PNU Visayas VMGO, the following were drawn: Based on profile of respondents, data showed that Female ranked 1, followed by Male as ranked 2. Those who preferred not to say ranked 3, and others ranked 4. Students ranked 1, teachers ranked 2, alumni, admin staff, and other stakeholders followed as ranked 3, 4 and 5 respectively. The respondents possessed a full awareness of the VMGO as ranked 1. A very high acceptability level was drawn as ranked 1.

Recommendations

The researchers would like to recommend that PNU Visayas put more effort into promoting the VMGO of campus to the students, Faculty, Administrative staff, Alumni, and other stakeholders. Explain its significance to the community to further enhance their knowledge and ideas about PNU Visayas VMGO. The researchers also suggest that the university shall implement a strong and effective way of relaying the VMGO to the students, and other members of the community to be able to accept its value and

relevance to the life of the stakeholders. In order to enhance or increase the level of awareness, stakeholders of the university should continuously collaborate and work for an intensive effort through a planned program of activities in promoting the VMGO. University Officials and personnel together with the faculty and students should constantly include the VMGO in the contest, Orientation seminars and among others. Web administrators should maximize the use of the university website to get the widest dissemination of VMGO. The official University Facebook should increase and continue to disseminate information about VMGO. Evaluation on awareness and acceptability of the VMGO by the various stakeholders should be implemented periodically.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers sought an approval from the university administrators/heads. After the approval, the permission from the Head of the Quality Assurance to conduct the questionnaire was secured. The researchers guaranteed that all the data gathered from the respondents remained confidential. Moreover, trust needs to be established and that the respondents should be protected all the time.

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